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**The Redeemed Christian Church of God
Rural Development Intervention in
Famole Community, Kwara State,
Nigeria**

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Abstract

The main objective of this research study is to critically examine the role and impact of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) through its missionary work in the development of Famole village, a rural community under Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara state Nigeria. The study examined and compared the level of development in Famole community before and after the arrival of RCCG missionaries to the community. A survey was conducted to find out the level of government contribution to development in Famole community, the study also sought to examine the contribution of RCCG intervention programmes to the development of Famole; the impact of such interventions as well as how to sustain the gains of RCCG intervention programmes were also examined. The research was carried out through qualitative research method; this involves survey questions, semi-structured interviews and focus group discussions. The research work was based on the Theory of Social Change. The study revealed that Famole community had never experienced development; it remained an abandoned community

for many years. The only identified government intervention in all its history was the fairly constructed feeder road which has never had any maintenance since its construction. The study discovered that RCCG's rural development approach to church planting impacted positively on the multi-ethnic Famole community, it resulted in better trust among the various ethnic groups living in the village. The study recommended that government, faith-based organizations and other stakeholders should emphasize on Development approach in providing for a better society.

Keywords: Famole Community, The Redeemed Christian Church of God, Rural Development

Introduction

Rural development has been a major concern for most developing nations of the world. In Nigeria, the term "rural" is a way of expressing or describing communities where there are little or no development activities compared to what is found in the urban areas (cities), especially in the areas of education, health, infrastructure, and other social development programs¹. Although the concept of rurality varies from one nation to another, the need for rural development is common to nations around the world.

Rural areas in most developing nations have the natural tendency to be neglected or not given priority in development matters. In some cases, rural development policies or programmes are discontinued whenever there is a change in government leadership². In other cases, prejudices in rural development policies have largely contributed to rural poverty, and this happens when the rural poor are exempted from the benefits of development³. Some of the biased rural development policies include urban preference in public infrastructural investment and the provision of security. This is the situation in most African nations. Rural development is mainly focused on humans and the environment; therefore, the development of rural areas calls for the provision of basic infrastructure and social amenities intending to enhance the quality of life for the rural populace⁶.

It is worthy of note, therefore, that the recent development plan of the federal government of Nigeria is now emphasising the public-private partnership in addressing development needs in rural communities in Nigeria¹¹. Non-governmental organizations (NGOs) are now being encouraged by Nigerian governments to participate in rural development

across the nation through the creation of enabling environments, tax holidays, and other favours from the government⁶⁶.

Various religious bodies in Nigeria have been doing their bits to improve the lives of the rural populace. This study, therefore, sought to investigate the role of Missionary activities of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (Hitherto referred to as RCCG) in bringing development to Famole rural community in Kwara State Nigeria and their contribution to the general improvement in the standard of living in community.

The Central Missions Board (CMB) of the Redeemed Christian Church of God (RCCG) had been giving serious consideration to Rural Development programmes as a better approach to reaching her goal of preaching the gospel and Church planting work in rural communities around the world. After a diligent survey work, Famole village, a rural multi-ethnic community in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara state was chosen as the community of interest for this research work. The reason for this choice is mainly because of the extent of neglect of the community by the government, there were no basic amenities and infrastructures in the community, more than five hundred children in the community were not attending school because there were no schools in the community, no health facilities, there is no electricity; although Famole community has been in existence for decades but they have not for once enjoyed the benefit of being connected to the national grid for their electricity supply till date. No potable water their only source of water was from a river (Oyi River) which strangely brought an outbreak of disease in 2021 that resulted in the poisoning of most children and the loss of a teenage girl in the community. Further survey revealed that Famole is a multi-ethnic community needing programme and activities that can bring unity and understanding among the many ethnic groups in the community.

Statement of the Problem

There has been limited study to evaluate the activities of religious institutions like RCCG on rural development. While studies have examined the socio-religious services offered by most religious institutions to rural communities in Nigeria, there is minimal attention to investigate how the RCCG extends and integrates its missionary work with sustainable rural development in important areas like education, health, provision of infrastructures, economic empowerment etc. Most significantly, there is a

dearth of study to evaluate the before and after effects of religious institutions in rural communities in Nigeria. Although RCCG has done a lot in the area of community development there has not been any academic work on the role of mission activities of RCCG in rural development hence the need for this research study. This study intends to provide a thorough investigation on the situation of Famole community in Ifelodun Local Government Area of Kwara state by looking at the trend of development before and after the intervention of RCCG missionary team as well as how the impact of their interaction could be maintained.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

The aim of this study is to investigate Redeemed Christian Church of God Mission work and Rural Development in Famole community Kwara state, Nigeria. The specific objectives are to:

- i. ascertain the level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community;
- ii. identify the areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community;

Research Questions

1. What is the level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community?
2. What are the areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community?

Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was adopted in this research work so as to accurately collect data and define the current position of missionary work of RCCG in relation to rural development in the study population. This method is considered suitable for this study because it enables the researcher to obtain and carefully record the true position of the issues being studied and also analyze the information obtained from the sampled population.

The study area for this research is Famole community under Ifelodun local government area in Kwara state Nigeria. Famole community was considered appropriate for the research work for two main reasons; Firstly, it was a community that lacked any observable development programme or

activity; there were no provisions of basic infrastructures, no schools and the living condition of the people was not good. Secondly, it was observed that there was no Church in the whole community. Since the main objective of this study is to investigate the role of RCCG missionary work in the development of rural Famole community, the two factors above make the Population of Study more suitable for the research work^{1, 2}. The above-mentioned reasons are also significant in achieving the RCCG's goal of Church planting through rural development programmes hence the choice of Famole community as the population of study.

The sampling technique used in this research is Purposive sampling technique³. This is a system of sampling in which the researcher intentionally selects participants that can provide valuable insights into the research questions⁴. In this technique individuals or groups having particular knowledge, skills or experiences relevant to the research question are carefully selected. In this research work, a total of seventy-six (76) respondents were purposively selected as samples for this study. The seventy-six participants were categorized into 34 respondents from questionnaire (designed in form of checklist consisting of sections A, B, C and D), 30 respondents were purposively selected for semi-structured interviews and 12 respondents were purposively selected for focus group discussion. The reason for this technique is because it was necessary to include the different ethnic groups living in the multi-ethnic Famole community most of who are largely uneducated. The respondents were selected with the help of the RCCG missionary and his wife who are serving among the population and are well familiar with the people of Famole community. The selection was carefully carried out from the various ethnic populations of Famole community as well as other stakeholders not resident in the neighboring communities like Gaa Lemam; these include parents of the students of The Redeemers Nursery and Primary School built by the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Famole Community. Other respondents include regular traders that carry out their economic activities in Famole markets on daily basis, few of these were former residents of Famole Community. The selected respondents from the study population were well familiar with the history of Famole community hence they are believed to be representative of the entire population.

As instrument for this research, the questionnaire was prepared in form of a checklist of items that are required as basic necessities for living a better

life in the rural Famole community. The questionnaire is made up of four sections namely, Section A, Section B and Section C as described below:

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of Respondents (N=76)

Variables		Frequency	Percentage
Sex	Male	64	84.21%
	Female	12	15.79%
Age Group	Below 20	7	9.21%
	21-30	11	14.47%
	31-40	19	25.00%
	41-50	33	43.42%
	51 & above	6	7.90%
Marital Status	Single	25	32.90%
	Married	51	67.10%
Ethnicity	Yoruba	46	60.52%
	Fulani	18	23.68%
	Nupe	12	15.80%
Education Status	Primary	19	25.00%
	Secondary	11	14.47%
	Tertiary	Nil	Nil
Occupation	Agriculture	66	86.84%
	Trading	6	7.90%
	Student	4	5.26%

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2023

Table 1 above shows that the 76 respondents are made up of 64 males and 12 females representing 84.21% and 15.79% of the population respectively. The age group consists of seven people (9.21%) below 20 years of age; they are the pupils of Redeemers Nursery and Primary Mission School, the age groups 21-30 were 11 (14.47%), 31-40 were 19 (25%), 41-50 were 33 (43.42%) and age 51 and above were 6 people representing 7.90% of the study population. The number of married individuals among the respondents was 51 or 67.10% of the respondents; the singles were 25 individuals or (32.90%) of the respondents. Famole is a multi-ethnic community consisting of

predominant Yoruba ethnic group, people of other ethnic groups as Fulani and Nupe were also living in Famole community. Forty-six (46) or (60.52%) of the participants were Yoruba, 18 (23.68%) were Fulani and the remaining 12 individuals or (15.80%) of the participants were of Nupe extraction. The education status of the participants was very low consisting of 19 individuals or (25%) with Primary education, 11 individuals or (14.47%) having secondary education and non with tertiary education. 66 individuals or (86.84%) of the participants were into agriculture as their occupation, 7.90% of the participants were traders while the remaining (5.26%) of the participants were students. From the demographic characteristics of the respondents above, it is obvious that Famole is mainly an agrarian community because the larger population of Famole community is involved in agricultural practices which consist mainly of livestock and crop production. Two of the traders interviewed were from a neighboring community to Famole.

Results and Findings

Research Question One: What is the level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community?

Table 2: The level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community?

S/N	Statement	A	FA	NA	B
1	Provision of feeder road	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
2	Potable water supply	-	-	34(100%)	-
3	Electricity supply	-	-	34(100%)	-
4	Hospital/Clinic facility	-	-	34(100%)	-
5	Health awareness program	-	-	34(100%)	-
6	Family Planning Program	-	-	34(100%)	-
7	Free Education/literacy program	-	-	34(100%)	-
8	School building	-	-	34(100%)	-
9	School feeding program	-	-	34(100%)	-
10	Coaching classes	-	-	34(100%)	-

11	Provision of books to students	-	-	34(100%)	-
12	Student Transportation system	-	-	34(100%)	-
13	Empowerment program	-	-	34(100%)	-
14	Interest-free Loan schemes for farmers/small businesses	-	-	34(100%)	-
15	Agricultural extension program	-	-	34(100%)	-
16	Provision of Agricultural machines	-	-	34(100%)	-

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2023

Key: Available (A), Fairly Available (FA) and Not Available (NA) and Beneficiaries (B)

Table 2 above revealed that all the 34(100%) indicated that provision of feeder road was made available by the government in Famole community and all 34(100%) respondents agreed that there were beneficiaries of the feeder road constructed by the government. The table also shows that all the 34(100%) respondents indicated that other basic infrastructural provisions as indicated in the table were not available in Famole community before the RCCG missionary engagement. The responses above revealed the deplorable situation of the people living in Famole community before the intervention programme of RCCG.

Research Question Two: What are the areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community?

The question above sought to examine the specific areas as well as the extent of rural development intervention by the Redeemed Christian Church of God through its missionary work in Famole village under Ifelodun Local Government area of Kwara State.

Table 3: Areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community

S/ N	Statement	SA	PA	NA	B
1	Medical Outreach programs	-	34(100%)	-	34(100%)
2	Hospital/Clinic facility	-	-	34(100%)	-
3	Potable water supply (Borehole water project)	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
4	Free Education/literacy program	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
5	School building	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
6	School feeding program	-	34(100%)	-	34(100%)
7	Coaching classes	22(64.70%)	-	-	22(64.70%)
8	Provision of books to students	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
9	Provision of free shoes and school uniforms to students	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
10	Empowerment program	-	28(82.35)%	-	28(82.35)%
11	Interest-free Loan schemes for farmers/small businesses	-	26(76.47%)	-	26(76.47%)

12	Health awareness/health care programs	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
13	Electricity supply	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
14	Agricultural extension program	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
15	Student Transportation system	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
16	Distribution of clothes and shoes to members of community	-	24(70.59%)	-	24(70.59%)
17	Adult education program	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
18	Provision of food during Christmas season	34(100%)	-	-	-

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2023

Key: Strongly Adopted (SA), Partially Adopted (PA), Not Adopted (NA), Beneficiaries (B).

Table 3 above reveals that 100% of the respondents indicated that the following intervention programmes were strongly adopted by RCCG missionaries in Famole village; Potable water supply, Free Education/literacy programme, School building, Provision of books to Students, Student Transportation System and Provision of food during Christmas season. The table also revealed that 100% of the respondents indicated that medical outreach programmes was partially adopted by RCCG missionary this is mainly because RCCG rural health intervention in Famole village did not include provision of full fledged clinic or hospital, it has been in form of occasional health checks and treatments and maternal health issues as need arises. 100% of the respondents also indicated that the school feeding programme was partially adopted by RCCG in Famole village because it has not been a regular occurrence. 82.35% of respondents believed that RCCG empowerment programme was partially adopted, 76.47% indicated that

Interest-free loan schemes for farmers and small businesses was partially adopted and 70.59% believed that distribution of clothes and shoes to members of the community was partially adopted by RCCG in Famole village, Clothes and shoes were usually distributed freely during gospel outreaches, some of the strong adherents of Islam in the community refused to attend such programmes hence could not benefit from the distribution of clothes and shoes. The table further revealed that 100% of the respondents indicated that some of the RCCG intervention programmes listed in table 4.3 above were not adopted by RCCG in Famole village these include Hospital/Clinic facility, Health awareness/Health care programme, Electricity supply, Agricultural extension programme and adult education programmes.

Presentation of Data

The analysis of the data collected and the discussion of the findings from the semi-structured interviews and focused group discussions carried out by the researcher is hereby presented. This presentation is mainly based on the research questions stated below.

Analysis of Research Questions

Research Question One: What was the level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community?

The question above was meant to examine the extent of government intervention in respect of development in Famole Village before the arrival of RCCG missionaries to the community. The result of the survey is as presented in Table 4 below.

Table 4: The level of development in Famole community before the arrival and missionary engagement by RCCG in the community?

S/N	Statement	A	FA	NA	B
1	Provision of feeder road	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
2	Potable water supply	-	-	34(100%)	-
3	Electricity supply	-	-	34(100%)	-
4	Hospital/Clinic facility	-	-	34(100%)	-

5	Health awareness program	-	-	34(100%)	-
6	Family Planning Program	-	-	34(100%)	-
7	Free Education/literacy program	-	-	34(100%)	-
8	School building	-	-	34(100%)	-
9	School feeding program	-	-	34(100%)	-
10	Coaching classes	-	-	34(100%)	-
11	Provision of books to students	-	-	34(100%)	-
12	Student Transportation System	-	-	34(100%)	-
13	Empowerment program	-	-	34(100%)	-
14	Interest-free Loan schemes for farmers/small businesses	-	-	34(100%)	-
15	Agricultural extension program	-	-	34(100%)	-
16	Provision of Agricultural machines	-	-	34(100%)	-

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2023

Key: Available (A), Fairly Available (FA) and Not Available (NA), and Beneficiaries (B)

Table 4 above revealed that all the 34(100%) indicated that provision of feeder road was made available by the government in Famole community and all 34(100%) respondents agreed that there were beneficiaries of the feeder road constructed by the government. The table also shows that all the 34(100%) respondents indicated that other basic infrastructural provisions as indicated in the table were not available in Famole community before the RCCG missionary engagement. The responses above revealed the deplorable situation of the people living in Famole community before the intervention programme of RCCG.

Research Question Two: What are the areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community?

The question above sought to examine the specific areas as well as the extent of rural development intervention by the Redeemed Christian Church of God through its missionary work in Famole village under Ifelodun Local Government area of Kwara State.

Table 5: Areas of rural development intervention by RCCG in Famole community

S/N	Statement	SA	PA	NA	B
1	Medical Outreach Programmes	-	34(100%)	-	34(100%)
2	Hospital/Clinic facility	-	-	34(100%)	-
3	Potable water supply (Borehole water project)	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
4	Free Education/literacy programmes	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
5	School building	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
6	School feeding programmes	-	34(100%)	-	34(100%)
7	Coaching classes	22(64.70%)	-	-	22(64.70%)
8	Provision of books to students	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
9	Provision of free shoes and school uniforms to students	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
10	Empowerment programmes	-	28(82.35)%	-	28(82.35)%

11	Interest-free Loan schemes for farmers/small businesses	-	26(76.47%)	-	26(76.47%)
12	Health awareness/health care programmes	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
13	Electricity supply	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
14	Agricultural extension programmes	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
15	Student Transportation system	34(100%)	-	-	34(100%)
16	Distribution of clothes and shoes to members of community	-	24(70.59%)	-	24(70.59%)
17	Adult education programmes	-	-	34(100%)	34(100%)
18	Provision of food during Christmas season	34(100%)	-	-	-

Source: Researchers' Field Survey 2023

Key: Strongly Adopted (SA), Partially Adopted (PA), Not Adopted (NA), Beneficiaries (B).

Table 5 above reveals that 100% of the respondents indicated that the following intervention programmes were strongly adopted by RCCG missionaries in Famole village; Potable water supply, Free Education /literacy programme, School building, Provision of books to Students, Student Transportation System and Provision of food during Christmas season. The table also revealed that 100% of the respondents indicated that Medical outreach programmes was partially adopted by RCCG missionary this is mainly because RCCG rural health intervention in Famole village did not include provision of full fledged clinic or hospital, but it has been in

form of occasional health checks and treatments and maternal health issues as need arises. 100% of the respondents also indicated that the School feeding programme was partially adopted by RCCG in Famole village because it has not been a regular occurrence. 82.35% of respondents believed that RCCG empowerment programme was partially adopted, 76.47% indicated that Interest-free loan schemes for farmers and small businesses was partially adopted and 70.59% believed that distribution of clothes and shoes to members of the community was partially adopted by RCCG in Famole village, Clothes and shoes were usually distributed freely during gospel outreaches, some of the strong adherents of Islam in the community refused to attend such programmes hence could not benefit from the distribution of clothes and shoes. The table further revealed that 100% of the respondents indicated that some of the RCCG intervention programmes listed in table 4.3 above were not adopted by RCCG in Famole village these include Hospital/Clinic facility, Health awareness/Health care programme, Electricity supply, Agricultural extension programme, and Adult education programmes.

Discussion of Findings

There were no schools, no hospital, and even dispensaries were conspicuously absent from the community. The whole community of Famole depended on untreated water from the Oyi River for drinking and other domestic uses. Agricultural extension programs, as well as agricultural machinery, were not in place. The living conditions in Famole were rather miserable because government infrastructures and other necessities for better living conditions were conspicuously absent. The intervention of the Redeemed Christian Church of God through its missionary adoption programme in Famole village is highly significant. The areas of rural development intervention by RCCG include provisions of basic necessities of life such as potable water, school project for children education, distribution of clothes and shoes to students and some members of the community, School feeding programme, Student transportation system, and interest-free loan for farmers and small businesses. The intervention programme of RCCG, as described above, is in perfect agreement with the sustainable development goals of the United Nations, specifically Goals 3, 4, 6, 8, and 10. The good side of the intervention is that beneficiaries of the RCCG intervention programme cut across all the different ethnic groups

living in Famole Village. this is in line with the main focus of SDG 10, which is essentially about reducing inequality within and among countries.

Conclusion

This study revealed that religious organizations can do so much in the area of development to provide a better life for the marginalized communities, especially in the rural areas. In this research study, it was clear that the missionary work of the Redeemed Christian Church of God in Famole community resulted in a significant transformation of the community. This study also reveals that The Redeemed Christian Church of God did not show religious prejudice or sentiments in their intervention plans for Famole community; people from other faiths benefited equally as the Christians in the community. The RCCG was able to uplift the status of Famole community through its community development intervention programs. These programs focused mainly on the following areas;

1. Education
2. Health care
3. Infrastructure (Potable water)
4. Economic

Recommendation

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations are put forth to encourage effective missionary efforts in ensuring better life for disadvantaged communities;

Recommendations for Faith-Based Organizations

1. Faith-based organizations should not engage in religious bias or sentiments in the process of spreading their faith.
2. It is recommended that Faith-based organizations should prioritize the well-being of people in their efforts to spread their faith, especially the Christian organizations that have the biblical mandate of fulfilling the “Great Commission Commandment” of Jesus Christ as stated in the Holy Bible;

“Go ye into all the world and preach the gospel to every creature” Mark 16:15
The best approach to fulfilling this commandment of Jesus Christ is people people-focused community development approach. Jesus Christ himself demonstrated this when he fed the four thousand and another five thousand

people in the course of his ministry work, he was also involved in healing the sick and providing comfort to the troubled; his ministry was focused on better life for the people he ministered to thus making a difference in their lives.

Recommendation for the Governments

Governments at all levels, local, state, and federal, should do their very best to encourage faith-based organizations and other not-for-profit organizations to be engaged in rural developments through partnership and also by providing enabling environment for their operations.

Furthermore, the government should enforce policies on rural development and be sincere enough to address the challenge of corruption in policy implementation, which allows government officials and contractors to divert funds meant for rural development to their pockets.

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